

An Interaction between distinct Families of Fermions? – 8 Theory

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Abstract:

This paper revolves around the question of interactions among fermions of different generation. Analysis is done via the new framework, 8-theory and in particular the equation predicting infinite families forming below first generation. Reader should be familiar with the 8- theory thesis to analyze this paper.

Introduction

$$M_{N+1} = \frac{M_N + (7)}{7 * \prod_{I=1}^r N_E} \quad (1)$$

$$M_{N+1} = \frac{M_N + (7)}{7 * \prod_{E=1}^r N_E} * \frac{1}{9} \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_{E+1} = 2E ; E \geq 1 ; E \in \mathbb{R}$$

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.11)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.12)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right) ; V \geq 0 \quad (1.2)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1) ; \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1) ; P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

We omit the second variation with the $1/9$ factor, as it is not necessary for this paper. This equation predict a fourth family below first generation. Now, can we correlate the degree of stability according to family is a very interesting question. If by third generation we have massive fermions but very unstable, which decay at very high speed, can we assume that at very light masses families (much lighter than first Generation), the families are very stable? We know protons are very stable, and protons Are bound states of first generation fermions.

So if this correlation is reasonable (particle physicists views are highly welcome here), we can assume that fourth family and below is incredibly stable. That assumption is coming to an agreement with the nature of dark matter, which is described as unvarying across the universe and only creating additional gravitational effect. The second question one would like to ask, given two distict families of fermions would they interact with each other at the same space? Can a T-quark effect a first generation Fermion?

Its seems unreasonable as the scales are much different, and from aesthetic point of view that is a major complexification of the 8 theory. However in the 8-theory we can combine the masses of generations and get to a higher generation masses. If the answer to the question above is negative, meaning that families do not interact with each other, it comes to an agreement with the dark matter do not interacting with our masses values and our fermions. Another problem is that additional families should obey the coupling constant equation:

Meaning, omitting bosons of different kind, and the additional families if taken to be dark matter do not behave in such manner as far as cosmology can derive. On the other hand, since their mass is infinitesimal, their behavior could differ by what we know in terms of interaction with other families and the coupling constant equation. The question of dark matter in the 8-theory framework is due to additional families forming; their mass is converging to zero. Their behavior and interaction is unknown, we assume stable and do not interacting with higher mass families. Due to their Infinitesimal total mass, whether they obey the coupling constant equation is unknown.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)